

THE ROLE OF HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF INNOVATIVE PROJECTS AND TECHNOLOGIES

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Abstract: The article analyzes the theoretical and practical aspects of the issues related to the role of higher education institutions in the production of innovative economic projects and technologies. Proposals aimed at improving the position of higher education institutions in the production of innovative projects and technologies have been developed.

Key words: Society, economy, innovative projects, technology.

Integration of science, education and production is one of the important factors in modernizing our national economy and increasing its scientific potential. In this sense, in recent years in our country, large-scale work aimed at increasing the efficiency of scientific and research activities, increasing innovative activity in the real sector of the republic, and strengthening the role of science in social and economic development is being carried out.

As a priority in the countries of the world, the problems related to the production of innovative projects and technologies in the higher education system are kept alive. The increasing globalization processes that are taking place today require the training of highly qualified personnel for each country. According to the UN Sustainable Development Goals, higher education is becoming a leading factor in the country's development. Based on the demand and need for specialists in developing countries, the scope of higher education is expanding more and more.

An innovation is a voluntary innovation that can be implemented and, as a result, can improve the efficiency of the industry in which it is implemented. Innovation is at the intersection of science, education and industry. In other words, the level of these three areas determines the quality of innovations to be created.

In order for innovations to be created, there is demand and investment for innovations in industry, infrastructure and qualified personnel for creating innovations in science, and an up-to-date system in education. Innovation is built on these three pillars.

An innovative project is a system of a set of actions aimed at achieving certain goals in the development of science and technology. They are interrelated performers activities, deadlines and resources. The innovation program is called a target project to support complex connected innovation projects, as well as activities in this direction.

The rate of training of highly qualified personnel in the world has increased dramatically, and the number of students will reach 414 million in 2030, which is a 4.2-fold increase compared to 2000 [1]. In the higher education system, scientific and research works are being carried out in various fields of science to improve the training of personnel. Special attention is being paid to researching problems related to the creation of modern methods of training highly educated personnel, the coordination of personnel training with the need for highly qualified specialists in today's labor market.

It is important to adapt educational programs to the requirements of international standards based on the in-depth study and analysis of advanced foreign experiences to increase the attractiveness and competitiveness of the higher education system in our country, and further expand cooperation in the field of education with developed foreign countries. becomes important. Fundamental improvement of the higher education system in the Action Strategy for the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021[2] and the development of public-private partnership in the field of higher education in the concept of the development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030, Based on the organization of activities of state and non-state higher education institutions in the regions, a number of tasks have been set to increase the level of coverage with higher education from 50 percent, to create a healthy competitive environment in the field [3]. In the higher education system, it is envisaged to introduce clear and new mechanisms for raising the quality of personnel training and ensuring the creation of necessary conditions for the training of highly educated specialists who meet international requirements.

The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education", the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 7, 2017 "On the Action Strategy for the Five Priority Areas of the Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan" Decree No. PF-4947 dated April 20, 2017 "On Measures for the Further Development of the Higher Education System" No. PQ-2909 dated July 27, 2017 "Economy in Improving the Quality of Training of Higher Education Specialists" PQ-3151, dated June 5, 2018, "On measures to further expand the participation of sectors and branches" "Increasing the quality of education in higher education institutions and their active participation in comprehensive reforms implemented in the country" Decisions PQ-3775 "on additional measures to ensure" dated July 11, 2019 "Measures for the reform of management in the field of higher and secondary special education" on" decree No. PF-5763, "Higher and secondary special education Resolution No. PQ-4391 "On measures to introduce new principles of management into the system" and "On approval of the concept of development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030" dated October 8, 2019 The dissertation presented serves as a specific source in the implementation of the tasks defined in Decree No. PF-5847 and other regulatory legal documents related to the field.

Innovative projects, as well as technical solutions and the ideas they understand, can have the following levels of scientific and technical importance:

- ❖ modernization (there will be no drastic changes in Base Technology); innovative (the new product design is significantly different from the old one); (Design created with leading technical solutions) developed;
- ❖ pioneering level (there are new technologies and materials that did not exist before).

The level of importance of the innovative project, especially for strengthening the process and casting results, determines the complexity and scope. This affects the content of project management.

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